

Uniting researchers and repositories to improve data FAIRness:

The Netherlands in a European perspective

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Executive summary

The European Research Data Landscape study aimed to present a detailed snapshot of the state of the research data ecosystem in Europe. Their researcher and repository surveys investigated the topics of research data management, sharing and reuse, and the current state of FAIR and open data. The study provided interesting insights and subsequent recommendations, and the data of the study was openly published to allow reuse. That FAIR practice allowed this paper to be created, where the focus is put on the subset of data specific to the Netherlands. This paper investigates the survey data in the Dutch context, comparing it to the European sample, and more importantly comparing it to the desires and ambitions there are for further improvement.

This paper highlights some interesting trends and patterns in the Dutch research data landscape, which help to identify potential areas of focus and approaches to improve the current picture.

- **FAIR is on the radar**, but general awareness and some specific practices continue to require dedicated support and incentives;
- **Software is on the rise** in the Netherlands at an advanced level compared to the European trends. This development brings along new questions, desires, and requirements for support, clarity, and standards;
- **Understanding is key** for improvement and progression. Researchers and repositories need to put in effort to get to know each other better, speak the same language, and understand what they can mean to each other.

The Netherlands are currently in a well-advanced position when it comes to research data management and FAIR practices. Past and current activities in the national scientific landscape have been fruitful, but continuous ambition can be fostered by evaluative exercises, such as the data analysis done in this paper, that can reveal new or different approaches to further advances. This paper highlights that researchers and repositories should focus more on coming together and explaining their perspectives, needs, and the support they can offer each other. Such collaboration is necessary to advance FAIR beyond a point that individual efforts can reach. At a European level, wider collaboration is also identified as becoming increasingly important for further improvement of the scientific ecosystem, which is a development the Netherlands can and should be actively involved in to advance science on the larger scale.

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Background

What is the current status of research data production, management, depositing, and consumption in Europe? With the increasing awareness and recognised importance of open and FAIR data practices, how far along are we with implementing these all across Europe? And, more specifically, how is the Netherlands doing in comparison to the rest of Europe? There are different global efforts to capture the state of science, such as the State of Open Data¹ or the UNESCO Open Science Outlook². This paper considers the results of the European Research Data Landscape study, which was carried out by Visionary Analytics³, Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS), the Digital Curation Centre (DCC)⁴, and the European Future Innovation System (EFIS) centre⁵ over the course of June 2021 to July 2022. The Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (DG RTD) of the European Commission commissioned this project with the aim of obtaining a detailed characterisation of the research data ecosystem in Europe.

The project consisted of several studies focusing on gathering information about the current European research data landscape through targeting either researchers or repositories. It must be noted that the term 'European' in this study covers the EU Member States, Horizon 2020 Associated Countries, and the United

Kingdom. The final report from the project⁶ presented all the studies that were executed, their results, and concluded with several recommendations based on this extensive snapshot of information. All of this information can inform new policies and support actions from the European Commission with regards to open and FAIR data practices. Supplementary materials to this report have been published on Zenodo⁷, including study materials, datasets, and infographics displaying the results.

The different studies included two surveys, one for researchers and one for research data repositories, two analyses executed using the F-UJI FAIR data assessment tool⁸, and targeted interviews to create six case studies. These different methodologies were combined to present a thorough view of the European landscape, observed from different perspectives and different focus areas. Unifying this information creates the depiction of the full picture: What do researchers and repositories indicate as their current practices and what can be observed in the data about these practices? Do the gaps in the FAIRness of data match what researchers and repositories report they require support on? Do the perceptions and observable facts of the current European research data landscape match up?

1 <https://www.digital-science.com/state-of-open-data/>

2 <https://doi.org/10.54677/GIIC6829>

3 <https://www.visionary.lt/>

4 <https://www.dcc.ac.uk/>

5 <https://www.efiscentre.eu/>

6 European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, European Research Data Landscape : final report, Publications Office of the European Union, 2022, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/3648>

7 <https://zenodo.org/communities/erd121/?page=1&size=20>

8 Anusuriya Devaraju, & Robert Huber. (2020). F-UJI - An Automated FAIR Data Assessment Tool (v1.0.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4063720>

Zooming in on the Netherlands

As the national centre of expertise for research data in the Netherlands, DANS aims to translate international and higher-level developments into the context of the Dutch research ecosystem. That is why, after the completion of the project, DANS has taken another look at the results of the different studies with a focus on the information relevant for Dutch researchers and repositories.

This paper presents the findings specifically from the two surveys conducted in the project that are related to the Netherlands, as well as comparing these to the whole European sample to showcase interesting trends and differences in the results. The main body of the paper is focused on the results and conclusions. Notes on methodology and other contextual information that is important for transparency's sake, but distracting from the main purpose of the paper, are presented in endnotes.

Repository survey

The survey for research data repositories was distributed between December 2021 and February 2022. A total of 316 responses were collected, 211 of which were complete responses and 105 responses were partial. Out of those responses, 10 came from Dutch repositories (9 complete responses, 1 partial response)¹. Given this, the Netherlands was one of the best represented countries in the sample, after Germany and the United Kingdom, together with France and Switzerland.

The goal of the survey was to assess the responsiveness and readiness of repositories with respect to the implementation of the FAIR principles. The survey included questions regarding the services and policies of the repository, the funding and costs, and influencing factors on their operations. The subsections below present the most important findings ordered by overarching topics.

Repository characteristics

We observed no significant differences between the Dutch sample and the full sample of the original analysis on most areas of the repository survey. There are many similarities in the distribution of repository types, the ages of the repositories, data volume and quantity, and the growth in these areas. Over half of the Dutch responding repositories have experienced growth in the last three years in the volume and quantity of the data they hold, in some cases more than doubling their holdings.

Out of the ten Dutch repositories, two were certified with a cybersecurity standard at the time of the survey. Five knew they were not, and three were unsure or did not have the information available. This is a different ratio than the full European sample shows, where only 9%ⁱⁱ of repositories were certified, 41% knew they were not, and 19% was unsure (and 31% of respondents did not answer this question). Therefore, when considering this data proportionally, more repositories are certified with a cybersecurity standard in the Netherlands than in Europe at large.

Respondents were also presented with a couple of statements and asked to indicate which apply to their repository. From this, we gather that seven out of the ten Dutch repositories have a continuity plan, adequate funding and sufficient qualified staff to address technical data and metadata quality managed through a clear system of governance, an explicit mission to provide access and preserve data in its domain, and mechanisms to secure ongoing expert guidance and feedback (either in-house or external). Six of the Dutch repositories also offer explicit information online about their policies and services. These survey questions mimic the formulation of

some of the CoreTrustSeal Trustworthy Digital Repository Requirements⁹. All of these results are proportionally higher than the European landscape in general, where scores on these topics were 20 to 35 percent lower. In terms of technical characteristics, the Dutch repositories also scored well on operating on well-supported infrastructural software (70%), using hardware and software that are appropriate for the services they offer and relevant to their Designated Communityⁱⁱⁱ (60%), and providing for protection of the facility and its data, products, services, and users (60%). For the full European sample, these numbers are all around 50%.

9 CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board. (2022). CoreTrustSeal Requirements 2023-2025 (V01.00). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7051012>

Finances and costs

It is good to see the survey data indicate a relatively stable financial climate for repositories. Many repositories indicate receiving structural funding (i.e. central funding or contract from a research or infrastructure funder that is in the form of a longer-term, multi-year contract) or being funded by the host institution curating the repository (i.e. direct or indirect support from the host institution). Beyond that, we also observed funding being received through value added service fees and projects funding the repositories.

In terms of costs, repositories indicate mostly incurring (in order of magnitude): staff costs, costs of maintenance and development of systems, and costs of preservation and storage (in the last year). Most respondents indicate not being aware of the approximate proportions of the different types of costs associated with running the data repository in the last 12 months. This could indicate limited financial insight in the organisation, but could also reflect that the representatives of each repository that responded to the survey did not have expertise in this specific area.

Services

The services that are being offered by Dutch repositories, apart from data storage, are most often 'Cataloguing and searching via metadata', 'Creation of persistent identifiers (PIDs)', and 'Value added services helping with compliance towards data reporting standards and/or metadata'. Services like 'Value added services providing information on the repository' and 'Value added services providing information on the stored data records' are least often indicated as being provided by the Dutch repositories. Proportionally, less Dutch repositories offer services providing information on the stored data records compared to the European landscape as a whole. However, more Dutch repositories offer services on 'data storage', content based searching, and 'value added services helping with compliance towards data reporting standards and/or metadata'.

Services

Repositories were also asked about the outsourcing of their services. The service most often indicated as outsourced is the creation of PIDs (50% of Dutch repositories and 20% of European repositories outsource this service). From the Dutch sample, 40% of the repositories also indicated not outsourcing any of their services (compared to 33% of European repositories). None of the Dutch repositories indicated they outsource

any of their value adding services, communication and dissemination, or customer support. In some cases, data storage (10%), cataloguing and searching services (10%), and policy or licence-based access control (20%) are outsourced for Dutch repositories. The latter is a noticeable difference from the European sample, where only 2,5% of respondents indicated outsourcing this service.

Dutch repositories also score well on having documented processes and procedures in place for managing the archival storage of data and having defined workflows for their services and processes from ingest to dissemination. Focusing externally, repositories were asked about the machine-actionability of their metadata and whether repository holdings are being made visible to aggregator services (e.g. data catalogues and portals).

Statement

Curation

Dutch percentages for the different levels of curation that are being performed by the repository were considerably higher than that of the European sample. Repositories were encouraged to select all curation levels that they apply to deposited data, knowing that not all deposited datasets will receive the same level of curation by the repository. Only a small percentage of repositories indicated they accept content as is, without performing any curation (10% of Dutch repositories, 15% in the European sample). Basic curation, described in the survey as activities such as brief checking, addition of basic metadata or documentation, occurs most frequently in the

European landscape, with 70% of Dutch repositories and 42% of European repositories performing this level of curation at times. More enhanced curation (e.g., conversion to new formats, enhancement of documentation) is performed by half of the Dutch repositories, opposed to only 32% of European repositories. A similar difference can be seen for data-level curation, which was defined as enhanced curation, but with additional editing of deposited data for accuracy, which 40% of Dutch repositories perform compared to 19% of European repositories.

Repositories also reported on the conditions they set for data to be deposited with them. Dutch repositories indicated more often that they require the use of data standards, metadata standards, and a licence defining data accessibility. Other conditions, such as the exclusion of personal data and third-party data, also occur more frequently in Dutch repositories, though these percentages are much closer together. The only condition Dutch repositories uphold less often than the general European landscape is the use of persistent identifiers. This result is a bit odd, since many Dutch repositories do offer the service of PID creation, but do not seem to require it for the data deposited with them. Half of Dutch repositories also focus on the understandability of the data for end users and define criteria for data and metadata to this end.

Conditions for deposited data

Preservation

80%

OF THE DUTCH REPOSITORIES
PRESERVE FOR A LIFETIME

In terms of preservation, most Dutch repositories never delete data after a specific amount of time, but rather preserve for the lifetime of the repository (80%). Most repositories also give depositors a guarantee for a specified minimum preservation period (70%). Dutch repositories indicated significantly more often than the European sample that they guarantee the integrity and authenticity of the data (60% vs. 28%). A similar difference is observed when considering the enabling of data reuse over time (80% of Dutch repositories compared to 50% of European repositories).

The survey also covered the topic of licences, asking repositories about the licences they use as a basis for their standard terms and conditions for data access. Only half of the respondents to the survey supplied this information, with 28% of European repositories using Creative Commons¹⁰ licences.

In the Netherlands, 40% of repositories use Creative Commons licences. Looking at the different types of Creative Commons Licences, Dutch repositories use CC0 most often (40%), whereas the European sample indicated CC BY as most used (22%). All Creative Commons licence types (CC0, CC BY, CC BY SA, CC BY NC, CC BY NC SA, CC BY ND, CC BY NC ND) are used to some capacity by Dutch (and European) repositories, but numbers are overall quite low. This data is somewhat difficult to interpret, since no 'other' types of licences were indicated or specified, but more Dutch repositories than those providing licence specifications indicated previously that a licence is a condition for data deposition. It remains unclear what licences other repositories use in practice and how they are specified. Thirty percent of the Dutch repositories indicated having a policy to deal with non-compliance of licensing terms when this is detected, compared to only 18% of European repositories. More Dutch repositories also seem unsure or unable to report on this topic (30%) compared to European repositories (12%). Again, this could be due to the role and areas of expertise of the specific respondents, or it could indicate a lack of transparency or clarity within the organisation. Monitoring compliance of the application and use of licences is indicated by 30% of Dutch repositories and 25% of European repositories.

¹⁰ <https://creativecommons.org/>

Policies

The survey asked respondents to indicate all the types of government or international organisations' policies that their repository has to comply with. None of the Dutch respondents reported that there were no policies applicable to them. Most often applicable are policies to do with personal data protection and policies related to the responsible management of research data in line with the FAIR principles (70% in both cases), which is quite a bit higher than the general European landscape (43% and 42%, respectively) though we do see the same trend of

these types of policies being indicated most often. Sovereignty policies^{iv} were indicated least often (20%). None of the Dutch respondents indicated they did not know or could not answer this question, so repositories seem to generally feel aware about the policies relevant to them. From the Dutch repositories, 70% also indicated they 'ensure, to the extent possible, that data are created, curated, accessed, and used in compliance with disciplinary and ethical norms', compared to only 42% of repositories European-wide.

Repositories' perspective on influencing factors

Repositories were also asked about their view on certain factors that could influence the current research data landscape. Respondents were asked to judge the level of influence different stakeholders could have in motivating researchers to make their data FAIR. Many indicated themselves, research data repositories, as one of the stakeholders that are influential in this area, after funding bodies. Departments or faculties were also indicated as influential by many respondents. Government or national ministries, research infrastructures, institutions or research performing organisations, community norms, and publishers or journals were less often indicated as influential by the Dutch repositories. Analysis of the full European sample shows that funding bodies are also

indicated as influential most often here. However, this stakeholder was then followed by publishers or journals and community norms in the European sample, and only then we see the research data repositories being judged as being influential. It is interesting to see that apparently the Dutch repositories take more responsibility in their own sphere of influence and seem to expect less from journals and community norms than repositories elsewhere do. The perspective of having a lot of influence is a good starting point for using this influence to improve certain areas of the research data landscape. The same question was posed in the researcher survey, from which the results are discussed in the next section.

How influential in motivating researchers to make their data FAIR are the research data related policies of the following stakeholder groups in your opinion?

Other influencing factors that were questioned were those related to policy. Respondents were asked about their affective judgement of the impact of certain policy factors on data FAIRness. In both the complete as well as the Dutch sample there is a clear negative judgement from respondents of introducing penalties to impose when data are not made FAIR. Other policy factors, such as monitoring compliance to policies, rewarding FAIR

behaviours, and making easy to understand policies are all generally judged positively. The most appreciated policy factor is to provide support for researchers to make data FAIR. The opinions of the Dutch repositories do not differ from the full sample on this topic, which is why the figure only displays the Dutch results.

How do you believe the following policy factors would influence data FAIRness?

Researcher survey

At the same time that the repository survey was distributed, a separate survey was distributed among researchers. This survey focused on the production, depositing^v, and consumption of data. Questions on the maturity, readiness, and responsiveness related to the implementation of the FAIR principles were also included in the survey. After data cleaning, the total number of responses was 15,066^{vi}. From this full sample, 422 responses (334 complete, 88 partial) came from respondents with their primary affiliation located in the Netherlands^{vii}, making up 3% of the full sample. Contrary to the repository survey, the Netherlands were not one of the most represented countries in the researcher survey, ranking 11th place in the full list of country responses¹¹.

The sample composition of the Dutch respondents matches the full sample in terms of age spread, career stage, and main role indicated. In terms of the primary field of science, the Dutch sample had a somewhat larger contribution from the Medical and Health sciences, but otherwise was also comparable to the full sample. The primary institutional affiliation types also matched the full

sample, with most respondents affiliated with a public university or public research organisation.

The sections below describe the most remarkable and relevant results from the researcher survey, focusing on where scores differ between Dutch researchers and the full European sample.

11 See p.17 of the original study report: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7351121>

Production of research data

The researcher survey posed many questions related to the production of research data and the activities that are carried out to this end. Some interesting questions in which Dutch researchers scored differently from the full European sample are highlighted here.

DUTCH RESEARCHERS PRODUCE MORE SOFTWARE AND CODE IN THEIR RESEARCH.

First, Dutch researchers indicated more often that they produced software or code in their current or latest research activity (30,33% vs. 21,76%). Similar to the full European sample, quantitative tabular data is the most often produced data type. The size of the produced data also does not differ meaningfully with the European landscape, with data often being either very small (<20 Megabyte) or very large (> 1 Petabyte) and most respondents actually indicating they do not know the approximate size of their most recently produced data.

In terms of documentation accompanying the data, Dutch researchers more often report providing descriptive documentation and metadata (53,55% vs. 44,06%) and administrative documentation (18,25% vs. 10,91%). Technical documentation is also often provided, whereas documentation related to use and preservation are less often reported.

DUTCH RESEARCHERS INDICATED MORE OFTEN THAT THEY CREATE A DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN WHEN STARTING THEIR RESEARCH

Several different activities are undertaken during any study or project. When asked about certain specific activities, Dutch researchers indicated more often that they create a data management plan when starting their research (31,99% of Dutch researchers do this always, compared to 22,49% of the full sample). Other activities that were often indicated were the use of researcher identifiers such as ORCID¹², the use of community standards for data and metadata, and describing data using controlled vocabularies. Somewhat less often indicated were acquiring globally unique and persistent identifiers, especially for software and code, and releasing datasets with a clear and accessible data usage licence. Overall, Dutch researchers did not score meaningfully differently on these activities compared to the full European sample.

The survey also posed questions about what standards researchers adhere to, to which Dutch researchers indicated more often that they adhere to standards set by the specific research community and the discipline. To a lesser extent, but still more often than European researchers, Dutch researchers adhere to standards set by the research data repository. Overall, standards set by governmental bodies and the industry are least often adhered to. In terms of content and focus areas of the standards, Dutch researchers adhere most to methodological standards. Much less often do researchers adhere to standards related to data processing, data description, measuring standards, or standards covering

variable description. The data does not discern whether researchers perceive a lack of such standards in their environment, lack understanding of them, or simply choose to not adhere to them.

After the completion of data production, Dutch researchers more often indicate that they share their data or are planning to do so (56,87% vs. 49,10%). After indicating this, researchers were also asked what they see as the (potential) relevance of their data for others. The largest share of respondents indicated here that they only see a relevance for the research activity it was originally produced for (77,49% of Dutch respondents and 72,58% of the total European sample). Least often indicated by both groups was that the data could be useful to help understand or reproduce the outputs of the original research activity. The largest part of the other options was more often indicated as relevant by Dutch researchers, including 'potentially relevant for others to reuse for other purposes', 'potentially relevant for others to replicate my research', 'potentially relevant for others to validate my research data', and 'potentially relevant for reviewers of my research'. Dutch researchers could also think of more other types of relevance of their outputs, however, the free text answers were not included in the public dataset. It is interesting to observe that (Dutch) researchers apparently do consider the replication and validation of their research, but not the understandability and reproducibility of their research by others. It would be interesting to further investigate this perception.

12 Open Researcher and Contributor ID, <https://orcid.org/>

With a desire to share data observed, we also consider access and rights to the data. For Dutch researchers, their employer is most often the rightsholder to their data, whereas for the full European sample the rights are most often in the hands of the researcher or their team themselves. This may cause obstacles for researchers in carrying out the sharing activities they personally desire, but this cannot be discerned from the data. For approximately ten percent of the researchers, the funder is the rightsholder. Publishers only hold the rights to data in approximately five percent of the cases in the Netherlands (compared to 10.69% in Europe). Considering the accessibility of published data, only less than two percent of researchers indicated offering their data publicly or open access without charge. Most researchers indicated specifying some restrictions around access to their data, for example, limiting access only to specific purposes or specific groups, or granting access only after ethical approval can be demonstrated. When asked who decided the level of access to produced data, most researchers indicated this being determined by themselves personally or someone else from their research team (e.g., their supervisor). The institution was also often indicated as the decision maker (or decision imposer), and a bit less frequently the funder was also named. Publishers were least often indicated.

Determining access requires a clear licence that details usage conditions and restrictions. Only a small number of

respondents indicated certain conditions in their licences. Trends were similar for Dutch and all European researchers, with attribution requirements named most frequently (18,01% vs. 13,70%). The second category most often indicated was that the respondent did not know about the conditions, followed in frequency by 'I do not set licences for my research data'. Approximately eleven percent of respondents also indicated they waived rights or put the data in the public domain or set a non-commercial licence. These conditions are somewhat reflected in the answers to later questions regarding the use of Creative Commons licences, where most respondents (17,30%) indicated using a CC BY licence, followed by CC BY NC. Again, many respondents did not know about Creative Commons licence use (25,36%) or indicated not using one (14,93%). The CC0 waiver was only selected by less than five percent of the respondents, which does not map to the eleven percent indicating their licence put their data in the public domain. It could be that those researchers use a non-Creative Commons licence to facilitate this.

Researchers were asked what their reasons were for setting restrictions on their research materials. The most often indicated answer for Dutch researchers (11,85%) was that they could not share their data due to data protection regulations. For the European sample, most researchers (9,63%) indicated that they intended to use their data for future publication before sharing it without restriction.

Reuse

Aside from producing and sharing their data, researchers were also asked about their habits in reusing existing data in their work.

MORE DUTCH RESEARCHERS INDICATED THAT THEY REUSE DATA MADE AVAILABLE BY RESEARCHERS OUTSIDE OF THEIR RESEARCH TEAM IN THEIR WORK

Dutch researchers tend to reuse observational data, software and code, and quantitative tabular data more often compared to the full set of European researchers. In general, the main reason for researchers to not reuse any materials is that they are not aware of any accessible and relevant materials being available to them. This could indicate that too little data is made available, or that there should be more awareness fostering about looking for data to reuse. However, approximately three quarters of all respondents indicated that they actively look for existing data to reuse in their research activities, so this practice does not seem to be lacking in researchers. Most respondents (both Dutch and European) agreed with the statement.

'THE AVAILABILITY OF RESOURCES THAT WE REUSED IN OUR RESEARCH ALLOWED TO REDUCE THE PRODUCTION OF NEW DATA'.

Respondents indicated less agreement with the statement that open science policies from funders encouraged them to reuse existing data instead of producing new data. This

indicates room for funders to be more outspoken to suggest this course of action.

The survey also inquired about the access and restriction levels associated with data that was reused by researchers. Public access was most often indicated, meaning the reuse was not restricted in any way. For both samples, the restriction of non-commercial or academic-only use was observed most often. When asked whether access and reuse conditions of data affected the choice to use or not use certain data, most respondents answered that it did not. Note that this does not mean the respondents did not encounter certain restrictions or conditions, but did not see them as an obstacle or influencing factor in the decision-making process.

Materials made available for reuse seem to have a persistent identifier less often in the Netherlands, with Dutch researchers indicating more often that they 'never', 'rarely', or only 'sometimes' see any persistent identifiers used in materials they want to reuse. This aligns with the finding that persistent identifiers are less often generated or assigned during production, even though many repositories do indicate offering the service.

Depositing in a repository

After observing the activities and perceptions of research data repositories in the previous section, the researcher survey provides an addition to this picture by collecting information from researchers about their use and perception of repositories.

Researchers were asked if they had ever stored data in a research data repository in their entire career. More Dutch researchers indicated that they had, though overall it can be observed that more respondents indicated they had not. Dutch researchers also indicated more often that they stored the usable data from their latest research activity in a research data repository. Respondents that indicated this option in the survey were asked some follow-up questions regarding the type of repository used. Dutch researchers indicated most often that they stored their data in institutional repositories, followed by international repositories. The same trend in repository types can be observed in the European sample at large, though the percentages are smaller. Funding body repositories and

commercial repositories were indicated least often by both groups. With regards to the data types that are stored in repositories, processed data is indicated most often, followed by data supporting publications and raw data. The percentages for these three categories were higher for Dutch respondents. Another interesting difference for this question is that Dutch researchers more often indicated storing software and code in repositories (19,67% vs. 9,28%). In most cases, researchers indicated that there were no costs associated with storing their data in a repository. In cases where costs were observed, these were most often covered by the institute of the researcher or the grant for the research project.

Different factors play a role in the decision to store data in a repository. Most often indicated were 'Acceleration of scientific research', 'Personal support for openness in science' and 'Dissemination and continuous higher impact of your research'. The next set of most indicated influencing factors were 'Norms of the research community', 'Funder's policy requirement', and 'Institutional policy requirement', which Dutch researchers also all indicated more often. Least often indicated by all respondents was 'National policy requirement'.

Respondents were also asked to indicate what factors influenced their choice for a specific repository to store their data in. The most indicated factor here was 'Repository's services are free of charge for researchers'. Other factors, such as the presence of a continuity plan to ensure ongoing (mid- and long-term) access and preservation of data, opportunities for persistent references and proper citation to allow for better discovery, and the certification of a repository (including security certificates) were also high on the list of deciding factors for researchers. Of least importance are

'Repository is commercial', the provision of metrics for tracking use, and the provision of curation.

Intentions around preservation were also questioned. The overall trend in the results is that most researchers indicate intending to keep their data indefinitely, the percentages decreasing as the time period decreases.

WHEN ASKED WHAT FACTORS CONTRIBUTE TO THE DECISION TO STORE DATA FOR A LONGER PERIOD OF TIME (MORE THAN FIVE YEARS), RESPONDENTS INDICATED THAT THEIR PERSONAL SUPPORT FOR OPENNESS, THE NORMS OF THEIR RESEARCH COMMUNITY, AND THE POLICY REQUIREMENTS AT THEIR INSTITUTION CONTRIBUTED MOST TO THAT DECISION.

The Dutch respondents indicated these answers more often than the full European sample.

The FAIR principles

The researcher survey also covered the FAIR principles, both in explicit and more covert ways. When asked how familiar they are with the FAIR principles, Dutch respondents indicated less often that they had never heard of them, and more often that they actively put them into practice compared to the full European sample.

This could reflect the history of the FAIR principles, which originated in the Netherlands¹³. In the project's final report, this question was also analysed for the subgroup of researchers that indicated having stored their data in a research data repository at least once in their career. We investigated the same question for the Dutch sample. In both cases, there is a clear pattern that shows that researchers who have deposited data in a research data repository at least once are more familiar with the FAIR principles than those who have never deposited in a

research data repository before. The Dutch sample even shows that over half of respondents that have deposited in a repository indicated that they actively put the FAIR principles into practice. This analysis cannot discern the direction of this relationship; does an increased familiarity with the FAIR principles lead researchers to deposit their materials in a repository, or might researchers become more familiar with the FAIR principles and practices by interacting with a repository to deposit?

How familiar are you with the FAIR principles? *

* No data for 16,82% (NL) / 21,35% (EU)

13 The Lorentz workshop 'Jointly designing a data FAIRPORT' held in Leiden, Netherlands, was the start of the designing of the FAIR principles. Workshop page: <https://www.lorentzcenter.nl/jointly-designing-a-data-fairport.html>; The workshop was also referenced in the Nature publication of the FAIR principles: Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. Sci Data 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

How familiar are you with the FAIR principles?

The four FAIR principles were also inquired about separately (“How important is it to you that other researchers are able to find your research / access your research / connect to your research / reuse your research?”). Much like the European sample, about half of

the Dutch researchers indicated all these four aspects as being important, with a distinction between Findability and Accessibility which were more often found important than Interoperability and Reusability.

When asked about support around making materials FAIR, Dutch researchers more often look towards their institutional support service and their peers, and less often to publishers or journal sites. Dutch respondents also indicated less often that they do not know where they would seek this support, which could be a result of clear communication and signposting about available support

to Dutch researchers. The survey then posited the question on who should be the one providing such training according to the researchers. Both the European as well as the Dutch sample ranked the different levels the same way, with the institutional level and disciplinary level at the top, followed by the national level and cross-domain level and a thematic approach being ranked lowest.¹⁴

The launch of the thematic digital competence centres (TDCCs) in the Netherlands this past year may shift this ranking in the coming years with their targeted approaches to increase thematic levels of support¹⁵.

If you require help to manage, share and/or make your data FAIR, where do you seek support? *Please select all that apply*

¹⁴ <https://tdcc.nl/>
¹⁵ <https://tdcc.nl/>

Open science

DUTCH RESEARCHERS ARE MORE AWARE OF THE EU OPEN SCIENCE POLICY

Apart from the FAIR principles, researchers were also questioned about open science. Respondents were asked if they were aware of the EU's open science policy¹⁶, which was true for more than half of all respondents; Dutch respondents confirmed more often than the European sample (65,40% vs. 53,51%). Researchers could then indicate how the policy affects their practices with regards to research data management and data sharing, selecting which practices they felt more encouraged to undertake: writing a data management plan, making data as open as possible, making data more FAIR, or reusing existing data instead of generating new data. All four of the questions were more often affirmed by Dutch researchers than the full European sample. Researchers also indicated whether their personal support for openness in science was a

contributing factor in the decision to store their data in a research data repository and to store their data for longer than five years. In both cases,...

...DUTCH RESEARCHERS MORE OFTEN INDICATED THAT THEIR PERSONAL SUPPORT FOR THE OPEN SCIENCE MOVEMENT CONTRIBUTED TO THESE DECISIONS (25,59% vs. 15,15% FOR STORING IN A REPOSITORY AND 21,33% vs. 12,33% FOR PRESERVING FOR LONGER THAN FIVE YEARS).

¹⁶ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science_en

Researchers' perspective on influencing factors

As was done in the repository survey, researchers were also asked to judge the level of influence different stakeholders could have on their research data management and sharing practices^{viii}. For Dutch researchers, research performing organisations and funding bodies were most often indicated as being very influential. Publishers or journals, community norms, and governments and national ministries followed. Interestingly, repositories as well as research infrastructures were not often indicated as influential by the researchers. In the Dutch sample, the share of

respondents indicating those two as 'not influential' was larger than in the European sample, though the overall trends were similar. This is very different from the view that the Dutch repositories have on this topic, as they scored themselves as the most influential stakeholder after funding bodies. It seems as if this self-identified potential for influence is not being perceived or experienced by researchers, which indicates a clear area of potential improvement and alignment between these stakeholders.

How influential in motivating researchers to make their data FAIR are the research data related policies of the following stakeholder groups in your opinion?

Researchers were also asked about policy factors that could influence their behaviour in terms of sharing and making their materials FAIR^{ix}. Much like the repository survey, there is also a clear negative attitude observed here towards introducing penalties for non-compliance, with Dutch researchers being even more outspoken about their negativity towards this compared to the full European sample. Judged more positively, but also with a lot of neutrality, both by Dutch and European researchers, was the introduction of compliance monitoring of policies.

Offering rewards for compliance was judged a bit more positively, with more Dutch researchers judging this as a positive influencing factor (38,63% vs. 29,88%). The clearest positive attitudes were found for providing support and making sure policies are easy to understand and adhere to. In both these cases, Dutch respondents more often expressed their positive perceptions of these factors. Overall, Dutch respondents indicated less often that they did not know or could not answer these questions.

Which of the following policy factors would positively or negatively influence you to share your data and/or make it FAIR?

Lastly, researchers were also asked about the factors that they see as the main obstacles to research data management and data sharing. Interestingly, Dutch respondents answered these questions proportionally more often. Both Dutch researchers and the full sample of European researchers, indicated 'time and effort required to manage and share data' and 'dealing with data protection and confidentiality requirements' as the biggest obstacles. This indicates that offering more support on these topics could lead to more data sharing and better research data management practices. Emphasising the

support roles that exist for these purposes, privacy officers and data stewards, could be a way to lower these obstacles. Efforts could be made on both the national and European level to improve these scores. A lack of data repositories and data centres where research data could be stored was least often perceived as an obstacle in both groups, with Dutch researchers reporting this considerably less often than European researchers as well. On all other obstacles, there is a slight trend with Dutch researchers identifying these factors as somewhat less of an obstacle than European researchers at large.

To what extent do you see the following as obstacles to research data management (RDM) and sharing?

Recommendations and specific actions

The original project, which consisted of more studies than covered in the current paper, concluded their landscape explorations with a set of recommendations and specific actions, clustered on different themes¹⁷.

The first noticeable observation to make from these recommendations is that the Netherlands are pointed to as an example of good practices multiple times. First, the Dutch National Coordination Point Research Data Management (LCRDM)¹⁸ is highlighted as an effort all Member States should consider creating and supporting on their own national levels. Also on the theme of local support, the effort in professionalising data stewardship

and identifying different models and types of data stewardship¹⁹ is highlighted as a specific action towards facilitating access to professional support that should be developed by all. Another LCRDM effort, the Do-I-PASS for FAIR self-assessment tool²⁰, is highlighted in the specific actions regarding the execution of self-assessment tools by Research Performing Organisations to review and improve their FAIR-enabling capabilities.

¹⁷ Chapter 7, starting on p. 176 of the original report: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7351121>

¹⁸ <https://lcrdm.nl/>

¹⁹ Mijke Jetten, Marjan Grootveld, Annemie Mordant, Mascha Jansen, Margreet Bloemers, Margriet Miedema, & Celia W.G. van Gelder. (2021). Professionalising data stewardship in the Netherlands. Competences, training and education. Dutch roadmap towards national implementation of FAIR data stewardship (1.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4623713>

²⁰ Taco de Bruin, Sarah Coombs, Jutta de Jong, Irene Haslinger, Henk van den Hoogen, Frans Huigen, Mijke Jetten, Jacko Koster, Margriet Miedema, Sjeff Öllers, Inge Slouwerhof, Ingeborg Verheul, & Jacqueline Ringersma. (2020). Do I-PASS for FAIR. A self assessment tool to measure the FAIR-ness of an organization (Versie 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4080867>

There are more recommendations and specific actions described that the Netherlands is already addressing in certain activities. For example, a specific action calls to the...

...DEVELOPMENT OF NATIONAL OR REGIONAL DATA STEWARD NETWORKS AND COMPETENCE CENTRES, AT WHICH LIMITED RESOURCES CAN BE POOLED.

In the past few years, many efforts have been made to develop and support digital competence centres (DCCs) at the local²¹, thematic²², and national level²³.

Fitting with the recommendation regarding awareness raising concerning the FAIR principles, the FAIR-Aware²⁴ self-assessment tool, developed by DANS, is a clear practical effort to that end. The tool, in line with the recommendation, focuses on the practical implications of the FAIR principles and how this supports the acceleration of science. Taken together, there are quite some nice efforts and activities ongoing in the Netherlands that show

continued prioritisation of the topics at hand: improving FAIR practices and good research data management, and professionalising and uniting the important stakeholders in the landscape.

Recommendations and specific actions that could receive more attention in the Dutch landscape include a stronger domain-specific focus on data management planning and monitoring that activities planned in data management plans are actually implemented. The structured and recurring use of automated FAIR assessment tools for repositories is also recommended, to identify where services could be improved to be more FAIR-enabling. Several recommendations are also made that point to pan-European collaboration efforts, which the Netherlands should also consider supporting and joining.

The overarching findings and conclusions from the European Research Data Landscape study are echoed in other global landscaping efforts, such as the State of Open Data and UNESCO Open Science Outlook. Common analysis results and subsequent conclusions and recommendations include the lack of dedicated support and credit and the need for pan-European efforts for further developments.

21 The Dutch Research Council (NWO), the national scientific funding body, has opened up multiple funding rounds for developing local DCCs <https://www.nwo.nl/en/news/digital-competence-centers-knowledge-institutions-forging-ahead>

22 Three thematic Digital Competence Centres have been developed in the Netherlands: <https://tdcc.nl/>

23 The LCRDM organised the Implementation Network DCC NL and hosts events and platforms for data stewards to come together for training and knowledge exchange <https://lcrdm.nl/dcc/>

24 <https://fairaware.dans.knaw.nl/>

Discussion – areas of improvement and looking ahead

The goal of the original report was to get insight into the full picture of the European landscape regarding research data. Specifically, to unite perceptions from the unique points of view of researchers and repositories and observable facts in the landscape with regards to FAIR principles and practices. Zooming in on the data that related to the Netherlands in this paper, some interesting trends and observations were found that point to areas of excellence and future improvement to be aware of.

FAIR is on the radar

Overarchingly, researchers and repositories in the Netherlands are aware of and familiar with the FAIR principles and actively put them into practice at a level that is above the European average trend. Self-reported perceptions indicate a strong personal support for the concepts of open science and FAIR, and intentions to follow policies and standards that implement those concepts are also expressed. However, there remains room for improvement, for general awareness raising as well as for the implementation of specific FAIR(-enabling) practices. Areas that showed the least implementation, or the least knowledge and understanding include the use of persistent identifiers, the setting of access levels and conditions, and the implementation of licences. Possibly,

the formulations of questions or unclear definitions in the survey led to lower results than should be realistically expected, though it should also be considered that these areas are generally less well understood and implemented by researchers and repositories in the Netherlands. Improvements in these areas could be established through a combination of spreading information to researchers more widely about the topics and choices to make, also in the form of data steward support, and monitoring that repositories offer the required services and support to facilitate the implementations. Aside from facilitating the desired behaviour, it is of course also important to incentivise it through a mechanism of reward.

Software and code on the rise

Another interesting observation is that the Netherlands concerns itself more with the management and processing of software and code than other European countries. Software and code are produced, deposited, and reused more often in the Netherlands than in the full European landscape. This advanced focus on that object type brings along new questions, desires, and requirements for support, clarity, and standards. It is important to match the

development of software production and reuse with the necessary support and policy. The NL-RSE network²⁵ already brings together Dutch Research Software Engineers from many different organisations to discuss overarching topics and exchange knowledge.

²⁵ <https://nl-rse.org/>

Understanding is key

An important factor in the overall effectiveness and development of the scientific infrastructure in a country is the alignment and mutual understanding between its core stakeholders. From these two surveys, it can be observed that there is somewhat of a mismatch between the perceptions of researchers and repositories about themselves and each other. For example, researchers do not seem to recognise or understand some of the services that repositories offer, even the services that repositories pride themselves on most or those that can be of most use

to researchers specifically. Dutch repositories indicated more often than the European average that they perform advanced levels of curation on their data. Researchers, however, indicated the provision of curation as being the least important factor for them in their decision to store their data in a repository. Similarly, metrics for the tracking of use of the data were ranked extremely low, even though there is a clear benefit of this service to researchers directly.

Another difference in perceptions is the fact that repositories indicate themselves as the second most influential stakeholder to help researchers implement FAIR practices, while researchers do not identify repositories as such, but rather one of the least influential stakeholders.

How influential in motivating researchers to make their data FAIR are the research data related policies of the following stakeholder groups in your opinion?

On a higher level, it was revealed in the researcher survey that an extremely low amount of open access data is published, which does not match with the observable facts²⁶. This raises the question of what is meant with 'publishing' and 'open access' and whether there are differing interpretations of such terms. Such differences in perceptions can make it hard to measure how well-aligned the stakeholders in the landscape are, but also makes it difficult for those stakeholders to speak the same language on such topics. To improve this, efforts should be made to inform and teach more about the roles, characteristics, and functions of the different stakeholders in the landscape in a way that breaches the silos experts can become stuck in, and thus is understandable to all. Funders should also be included in this effort, as one of the stakeholders identified by both researchers and repositories as very influential. However, researchers indicated at the same time that open science policies from funders do not currently encourage them to reuse existing data instead of producing new data, which identifies an area where funders can clearly use more of their influential status to foster change.

To truly achieve next steps in the level of awareness and implementation of FAIR in the Netherlands, it is essential that the different stakeholders in the landscape realise they are all working towards the same goal and each of them fills a different role in the process. Expressing that more clearly to each other in a way that emphasises how their services help each other and can save time and effort could lead to a breakthrough of the next few steps of development of science.

Taken together, the European Research Data Landscape study showed that the current snapshot of science in the Netherlands can be considered quite an accomplishment, but also something that is important to continue to nurture. Current activities and efforts are effective and will likely continue to be, but to be able to continue this position of excellence increasingly creative and bold additional actions are required. Though this paper focused on comparing our current state to that of Europe, this comparative act should not be our motivator when it comes to research data management and FAIR. We should remain in competition with ourselves and strive to remain in a forward trajectory. As identified in the European study, it is also becoming more and more important to join forces across all of Europe, to collect knowledge and resources at a level where it can make an incredible impact across countries. Such collaborations can be platforms to share what we are proud of, but also to solve issues or overcome obstacles that prove difficult to tackle on an individual national level.

²⁶ <https://netherlands.openaire.eu/search/advanced/research-outcomes?sortBy=resultdateofacceptance,descending&type=datasets&resultbestaccessright=%22Open%2520Access%22&year=range2023:2024>

Endnotes

- i It must be noted that the survey also contained 84 responses for which the question regarding the location of the repository was not filled in. These responses were either partial responses that did not answer this question, or the repositories appeared out of scope for the survey (i.e. does not hold research data) and were therefore redirected out of the survey before reaching this question. Although it cannot be discerned whether any of these responses could be attributed to the Netherlands, it can be concluded that these responses would only provide limited (if any) information if included, due to their partial nature. Another 72 responses indicated their location as 'other', from which it must be concluded the repositories reside outside of the specified European countries. All of the responses that cannot directly be attributed to one country have been included in the full sample analyses in the project's final report ($n = 316$), and therefore these results present a slightly wider scope than solely Europe.
- ii When percentages of responses are reported, they are always calculated against the full sample size, regardless of response rates for each question. This can result in different numbers presented compared to the original study, where totals were adjusted for response rates. As an example, if in a total sample of 10 respondents 4 answered 'yes', 2 answered 'no', and 4 did not answer the question, the original study would have reported that 66% (4 out of 6) answered 'yes', whereas the current paper would report that 40% (4 out of 10)
- iii Designated Community, as defined by CoreTrustSeal: An identified group of potential consumers who should be able to understand a particular set of information. The Designated Community may be composed of multiple user communities. A Designated Community is defined by the [repository] and this definition may change over time."
- iv The Dutch National Coordination Point Research Data Management (LCRDM) soon-to-be-published report '*Data sovereignty, data governance and digital sovereignty*' presents a definition of data sovereignty that fits the context of the current paper: "Data sovereignty refers to the level of control and autonomy an organization wields over their data. For example, in the context of data sharing, data sovereignty refers to the autonomy to determine how, when and under which conditions data can be shared." (p. 6)
- v In the context of research data, the term 'depositing' is used to indicate the archiving and/or publication of research data in a repository.
- vi In the full researcher survey sample ($n= 15066$), 11,725 responses were complete, whereas 3,341 were deemed partial responses. Responses were categorised as 'partial' when they were not complete, but answered at least one of the key questions and thus were not considered for removal.
- vii Similar to the repository survey, it must be noted that 154 survey respondents did not indicate any country to identify themselves with. From this group, 153 indicated 'other', and one respondent did not answer the question at all. Based on this it can be assumed that the survey was likely answered by researchers outside of Europe, presenting a slightly wider landscape than the intended scope in the full sample again.
- viii In this survey, the stakeholder category 'Departments and faculties' was not included in the question.
- ix In the researcher survey, this question offered three affective answer options, whereas the same question in the repository survey offered five. This causes the answer scores to be presented on different scales of intensity.